

Capital Structure and Effective Tax Rate in Listed Manufacturing Firms in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

In this study the author aims to evaluate the effect of capital structure on effective tax rate of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The scope of this study covers a 10-year period ranging from 2013 to 2022. The independent variables of interest which were employed in other to ascertain the possible effect include; leverage, long-term debt and short-term debt. Specifically, the author conducts pre regression analysis which includes descriptive statistics, correlation matrix, and normality of residua analysis. Basically, the pool Ordinary Least Square Regression analysis was first conducted, and diagnostic tests were carried out to check if it violates the basic Gauss Markov Theorem and assumptions. Particularly, the researcher finds that the outcome from the OLS estimator reveals that: leverage has a positive significant effect on effective tax rate of listed Manufacturing firms in Nigeria. ong-term debt has a negative significant effect on effective tax rate of listed Manufacturing firms in Nigeria; and short-term debt has a negative significant effect on effective tax rate of listed Manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Results from the robust standard error estimator leads to the conclusion that leverage can increase effective tax rate while short-term and long-term debt reduces the effective tax rate of the firms under consideration. This study recommends that governments be stricter in overseeing firm tax policies and practices by exploiting the loopholes contained in the taxation rules, one of which is by applying capital structure practices.

1. Introduction

Capital structure refers to the combination of debt and equity that a company utilizes to fund its assets. This method is used by public corporations to finance their assets, establish their capital structure, and determine the quality of their corporate governance. Determining the optimal capital structure is a challenging undertaking that requires diligent attention from the firm's management. Capital structure decisions play a crucial role in determining the value of organizations and the wealth of stockholders. The management chosen by stockholders serves as their representatives on the board of directors, with the responsibility of operating in their best interests.

Choosing the optimal financing decision among the available alternatives is crucial for ensuring the financial stability of a company. The capital structure decision, which is one of the three financing decisions alongside investment and dividend decisions, is a crucial responsibility for finance managers. The selection of the most suitable capital structure for different scenarios, taking into account the available investment options, is closely tied to a company's ability to meet the needs of its stakeholders. This fact emphasizes the significance of the decisions regarding capital structure that have been discussed previously. As stated by Abor and Biekpe (2015), the decision regarding capital structure is crucial as it directly impacts an organization's ability to maximize returns for its stakeholders and effectively compete in the market.

Maximizing shareholder value is a key objective for many firms. Accomplishing this would involve minimizing the expenses borne by the companies. Income tax is a crucial cost for firms as it directly impacts their profitability. Tax, on the other hand, plays a crucial role in the financial growth of a nation. It serves as a significant source of income for the government, enabling it to fulfill its objectives, including resource redistribution, employment generation, and economic development. Although taxes provide clear advantages to nations, the problem of tax non-compliance, including tax aggressiveness, has been a persistent issue in societies throughout history (Uadiale, Fagbemi, & Ogunleye, 2020). In their study, Mgbame, Chijoke-Mgbame, Yekini and Yekini (2017) discuss the concept of tax aggressiveness, which refers to various actions taken by management to reduce taxable income. These actions can be either legal or illegal, and are done with the goal of maximizing income.

In Nigeria, tax administration has been characterized by inefficiency and ineffectiveness, resulting in higher costs of tax compliance and a lack of clarity in the tax system (Maiye, 2022). The inefficiency is evident in the approach taken by the tax authority (Federal Inland Revenue Service, FIRS) when it comes to collecting revenue from companies. At times, tax officials may assign this task to external parties who employ unconventional approaches like sealing off the premises of companies, which can introduce uncertainty into the system (Maiye, 2022). Another concern arises from the potential for multiple taxes due to the overlapping of taxes from different levels of government. In certain cases, companies may find themselves having to make extra cash payments for taxes that they had already paid, as a result of government agents responsible for these deductions not remitting the funds (Nwaobia & Jajeoba, 2016). Due to various factors, companies may choose to implement strategies aimed at minimizing their tax burden. This could be driven by a desire to avoid inefficiencies in the tax system or to take advantage of financial incentives. They achieve this by utilizing all available legal avenues provided by tax laws to enhance their post-tax income.

Tax planning then becomes a crucial decision option for managers of firms. Managers have the ability to utilize tax planning to pursue personal gain and boost the company's earnings (Desai and Dharmapala, 2006). According to Lanis and Richardson (2011), the corporate landscape in many countries is characterized by managerial actions focused on reducing corporate taxes through aggressive tax strategies. These actions have both costs and benefits that are significant for management, shareholders, government, and society as a whole. In a recent study by Chen, Chen, Cheng, and Shelvin (2020), it is suggested that tax aggressiveness can lead to significant tax savings and the potential for rent extraction, which can be cleverly concealed within tax aggressive practices. Shareholders directly reap the rewards of these tax savings, while managers can also benefit if they are rewarded by shareholders for their successful tax management strategies. When managers engage in activities that do not prioritize maximizing firm value, it can be seen as extracting value from shareholders. A prime illustration would be the practice of engaging in aggressive financial reporting. There are several factors to consider when examining the costs associated with tax aggressiveness. These include the time and effort invested in tax planning activities, the transaction costs incurred during these activities, and the potential impact on reported earnings (Chen et al., 2020). In their study, Chen et al. (2020) suggest that the level of benefits and costs a firm can expect to receive will influence its level of aggressiveness.

Every business relies on financial resources to support their operations. Businesses obtain funds from both internal and external sources. External sources of funding come from the business owners and creditors who will be repaid in the future. Every finance manager must make decisions regarding the sources and allocation of funds to achieve the business's goals. The capital structure is formed by combining different debt and equity to make up the business's total capital. The capital structure decision plays a crucial role in determining the success of a business, as it has a direct impact on its profitability (Velnampy & Niresh, 2022). Similarly, decisions regarding the company's capital structure can have detrimental effects on its success or lead to financial difficulties.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Literature

2.1.1 Capital Structure

There have been several attempts to define capital structure, all of definitions explain the kinds of securities and the proportionate amounts that makeup capitalization. It is the mix of different sources of long-term sources such as equity shares, preference shares, debentures, long-term loans and retained earnings. One of these definitions for Gangeni (2006) that state the study of capital structure attempts to explain the mix of securities and financing sources used by corporations to finance real investment. The firm needs to make investments to at least remain in business, let alone display some growth. To finance these investments, the firms can use internal finance sources such as retained earnings and issuing shares for public or use external finance sources as a loans or bonds. The term capital structure refers to the relationship between the various long-

term sources financing such as equity capital, preference share capital and debt capital as Parmasivan and Subramanian (2009). Capital structure is the permanent financing of the company represented primarily by long-term debt and equity and deciding the suitable capital structure is the important decision of the financial management because it is closely related to the value of the firm. Gitman and Zutter (2012) defined capital structure as the mix of long-term debt and equity maintained by the firm. Although the actual levels mix of the firm's permanent long-term financing represented by debt, preferred stock, and common stock equity may vary somewhat over time, most firms try to keep their financing mix close to a target capital structure. According to Ehrhardt and Brigham (2011), the main purpose of the capital structure is to comprise of the optimal mix of debt and equity.

A firm's capital structure decision includes its choice of a target capital structure, the average maturity of its debt, and the specific types of financing it decides to use at any time. As with operating decisions, managers should make capital structure decisions that are designed to maximize the firm's intrinsic value. From the last definitions, the capital structure can be defined as the mixing of financial sources to finance the firm's operations. Financial sources can include the debt and equity that can be used by the firms. To maximize the firm's intrinsic value, the cost of capital structure must be reduced to the lowest level. When reach this point, that's mean the optimum capital structure is achieved. Optimum capital structure may be defined by Parmasivan and Subramanian (2009) as the capital structure or combination of debt and equity that leads to the maximum value of the firm. Optimum capital structure is the capital structure at which the Weighted Average Cost of Capital (WACC) is minimums and thereby the value of the firm is maximums. Deciding the suitable capital structure is important decision of the financial management because it is closely related to the value of the firm. Capital structure is the permanent financing of the company represented primarily by long-term debt and equity. Asaf (2004) states that the "Optimal capital structure means having the right balance of debt and equity financing in the business". Debt financing decisions for most corporations involves balancing a series of trade-offs involving cost, liquidity, choice of maturity, and the basis and frequency of interest rate resets.

2.1.2 Effective Tax Rate

Researchers over the years have adopted various measures of tax planning. One such measure is Effective Tax Rate (ETR). The average effective tax rate as used by Phillips and Regois (2000) is the ratio of total tax expenses to pre-tax income. Khaoula and Ayed (2002); Seyram and Holyto (2006) considered an effective tax rate as a measure of tax planning that decreases a firm's tax liability without necessarily decreasing its accounting income. Likewise, an effective tax rate for a corporation is the average rate at which its pre-tax profits are taxed. In the opinion of Inua (2018), Cash ETR is the tax rate which accounts for only taxes paid into the account, without deferred taxes and long-term analysis. Moreover, an effective tax rate does not accurately capture permanent difference between book and taxable income; hence it is often called a partial measure of non-conforming tax avoidance. Aggressive tax planning involves cost like reduced government revenue for important services like health care, hospitals, schools, security, aged care and support for people with disabilities, unfair competition for businesses that are complying with tax laws in the way the laws were intended to operate, transaction costs incurred in setting up the tax planning

strategy, such as registration and legal fees to establish off-shore subsidiaries, the risk of detection if the activities are illegal, or in the 'grey' area.

Empirical evidences reveal that the risk of detection increases as more firms engage in the same strategy, and with the length of period a firm pursues the strategy, the increased ability of managers to use the opaqueness required to disguise some transactions in order to extract rents for themselves, the incentives required to encourage the tax manager or director to engage in these activities, as they face personal costs if detected (Gupta & Newberry, 1997). Corporate ETR basically assesses the tax performance of firms. Thus, it is the best measure to evaluate the actual corporate tax burdens. ETR is a commonly used measure of a firm's tax burden that provides basic summary statistic of tax performance which describes the amount of taxes paid by a company relative to its profit before tax. Corporate Effective Tax Rates (ETRs) are often used by policymakers and interest groups as a tool to make inferences about corporate tax systems because they provide a convenient summary statistic of the cumulative effect of various tax incentive and corporate tax rate changes (Kern & Morris, 1992; Gupta & Newberry, 1997).

2.2 Theoretical Review

The pecking order theory was first introduced in 1961 by Donaldson but was later altered and modified by Myers and Maljuf in 1984. The theory regards what type of financing a firm prefers when it is in need of more funding, whether it is internal or external. In this situation, according to Ehrhardt & Brigham (2011), the firm first raises capital internally by reinvesting its net income and selling its short-term marketable securities. When that supply of funds has been exhausted, the firm will issue debt and perhaps preferred stock. Only as a last resort, the firm will issue common stock. A theory stating that, all other things being equal, companies seeking to finance a new project or product have a hierarchy of preferred financing options that progresses from the most preferred to the least preferred. The hierarchy is said to follow this order: internal funding (or simply financing a project or product out-of-pocket), debt issuance, debt-equity hybrid issuance, and equity issuance. The reasons why firms have that order of preference have to do with asymmetric information.

Asymmetric information occurs because managers have more information than the shareholders about the state of the firm and how well it is doing. The result is therefore that the shareholders will base their belief on the firm's future on the manager's actions. The manager's actions are believed to signal information about the state of the firm. According to (Malm & Roslund, 2013), issuing shares sends a message that the shares are overvalued, whereas issuing debt does not send any message. Debt issuing is therefore favored over equity issuing. As Olokoyo, (2012) said, if firms are required to finance new projects by issuing equity, underpricing may be so severe that new investors capture more than the net present value of the new project, resulting in a net loss to existing shareholders. As a result, managers will hesitate to issue equity if they feel that it is undervalued by the market. However, investors realize that managers will hesitate to issue new equity when it is underpriced. Thus, both managers and investors react according to their available information. Based on this argument, if managers tend to issue undervalued equity (low priced equity), the wealth will be transferred to the 24 investors against the shareholders' benefits and

wealth. In this situation, according to Al-tally (2014), internal funds and debt will be preferred to equity.

2.3 Empirical Reviews

Elena, Roberto, and Antonio (2023) examined the determinants of Effective Tax Rate (ETR) in emerging economies from a joint perspective, focusing on the BRICS (Brazil, Russia, India, China and South Africa) and MINT (Mexico, Indonesia, Nigeria and Turkey) countries. The study uses a sample of 7844 listed companies taken from the Compustat data base for the period 2006–2015 and applied panel data methodology. The dependent variable effective tax rates and the independent variable includes size, leverage, asset composition and profitability, firm growth, earnings management and deferred tax, Statutory Tax Rate, level of development, index of economic freedom, GDP growth and institutional quality. The study results show that both business variables and institutional factors have a significant effect on the tax burden for firms in emerging countries.

Balios, Tantos, Eriotis and Vasiliou (2020) investigated the determinants of the effective corporate tax rate of companies of the European Union (EU) discriminating between northern and southern economies. The study adopts the period after the outbreak of the crisis in the Eurozone up today including some years before 2009 in the assessed period. The Dependent variable is Effective corporate income tax rate, while the independent variable includes total debt, Financial leverage, Capital Intensity, Inventory Intensity, Research and Development Intensity and ROA. The study results point out that the effective corporate income tax rate is variously affected by firm-specific determining factors for both northern and southern economies.

Ajaya and Swagatika (2020) empirically investigated the factors deriving effective tax rate (ETR) for Indian manufacturing firms in different sectors. The study used Arellano–Bond dynamic panel regression model to identify the key drivers of ETR, and impulse response functions of panel vector auto-regression model to analyze the response of ETR because of one standard deviation (SD) shock to its key determinants. The dependent variable was effective tax rate and independent variable includes debt ratio (DR), asset tangibility (AST), non-debt tax shields (NDT), and firm age (AGE). The study finding reveal that in case of entire manufacturing sector, leverage and non-debt tax shield are driving ETR positively and asset tangibility is driving ETR negatively.

Barbera, Merello and Molina (2020) investigated the effect of the determinants of corporate effective tax rates (ETR) of listed companies in euro area. With a large and recent panel of 2,870 listed companies for the period 2005–2016, the authors use the generalized moments method (GMM) to estimate global models for three groups of countries and specific models for six selected countries: Germany, Spain, France, Italy, Belgium and Greece. The dependent variable effective Tax Rate while the independent variables include the variables Size, Leverage, Capital Intensity, Inventory In- tensity, R&D Intensity and Profitability. The results findings confirm that ETR has different determinants depending on the countries analyzed.

Flagmeier, Vanessa and Jens (2020) examined the visibility of the GAAP effective tax rate (ETR) in firms' financial statements as a distinct disclosure choice. The study applies a game-theory disclosure model for voluntary disclosure strategies of firms to a tax setting. The dependent variable is an effective tax rate while the independent variable includes firm leverage, total debt,

long term debt, equity to asset ratio, capital intensity and profitability. The study findings show that unfavorable ETR conditions are not highlighted, They observe higher disclosure visibility for favourable ETRs (smooth, close to the industry average, decreasing).

Bărbuță-Mișu, and Madaleno, (2020) examined the determinants of effective corporate tax rate for three listed companies from Eastern European Stock Exchanges - Bulgaria, Hungary, and Romania, for the period 2006-2015. The study uses multivariate regressions and different estimation methods (data panels with OLS EGLS and quantile regressions. The dependent variable effective tax rates and the independent variable includes financial leverage, equity ratio, and total debt. The study results show that for Romania, Bulgaria and Hungary managers are focused on the financial management, especially on capital structure, and less focused on fiscal management, in part, due to the lower taxation.

Delgado, Fernandez and Martinez-Arias (2019) investigated the relationship between the effective tax rate (E.T.R.) and company size in Germany to test tax planning political power versus political cost theories. The study uses a quantile regression approach. Data collected from Compustat, corresponding to non-financial listed companies during 1992–2009. The dependent variable effective tax rate and the independent variables includes leverage, inventory intensity and equity ratio. The results indicate a nonlinear relation, with a positive sign for the first quantiles and a negative one in the last part of the distribution.

Mascagni and Mengistu(2019) investigated corporate ETRs in Ethiopia and whether the distributional effects they have in practice are in line with the corporate tax policy design. The study uses profit tax at the numerator and gross profit at the denominator in the measurement. The dependent variable was effective Tax Rate while the independent variables include the variables Size, Leverage, Capital Intensity, and total debt. The finding result show that the U-shaped relation between size and ETR, indicating that small firms face the highest burden, while large firms still pay more than middle sized firms do the latter group being the one that experiences the lowest tax burden.

In 2019, Petr Janský aimed at contributing to ongoing policy debates about taxes paid by multinational enterprises and about changes in the system of international corporate taxation. The study used Orbis database to estimate ETRs across countries and over the years. The dependent variable effective tax rate and the independent variable includes debt to asset ratio, debt to equity ratio, short term debt to total asset and long term debt to total asset. The study findings show that there are differences in observed ETRs across countries and that many MNEs do not pay much tax in many countries.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design

Specifically, in this study, ex-post facto research design is employed. Ex post facto research uses data already collected, but not necessarily amassed for research purposes. Ex post facto literally means from what is done afterwards.

3.2 Population of the Study

The population of this study is made up of manufacturing firms from 6 sectors that are listed on the floor of the Nigerian stock exchange market for the period between 201 and 2021. As at 31st December, 2022 the total number of listed firms in these sectors are shown below:

Agriculture	5
Conglomerates	5
Consumer Goods	19
Industrial Goods	15
Natural Resources	4
Healthcare	11
Total	59

3.3 Sample Size and Sampling Technique

In a bid to deriving a sample size from the total population, the study adopted Krejcie and Morgan, (1970) sample size computation. Krejcie and Morgan's sample size calculation is based on $p = 0.05$ where the probability of committing type I error is less than 5 % or $p < 0.05$. Therefore, the sample size for this study is computed below:

$$S = \frac{x^2 NP(1-P)}{d^2(N-1) + x^2 P(1-P)}$$

$$S = \frac{1.96^2 \times 59 \times 0.5 (1-0.5)}{0.05^2(59-1) + 1.96^2 \times 0.5 (1-0.5)}$$

$$S = \frac{3.8416 \times 59 \times 0.5 (1-0.5)}{0.0025 (59-1) + 3.8416 \times 0.5 (1-0.5)}$$

$$S = \frac{226.6544 \times 0.5 (0.5)}{0.0025 (59-1) + 3.8416 \times 0.5 (1-0.5)}$$

$$S = \frac{226.6544 \times 0.5 (0.5)}{0.0025 (58) + 3.8416 \times 0.5 (0.5)}$$

$$S = \frac{226.6544 \times 0.25}{0.145 + 3.8416 \times 0.25}$$

$$S = \frac{56.6636}{0.145 + 0.9604}$$

$$S = \frac{56.6636}{1.1054}$$

$$S = 51.26$$

However, firms that got listed after the study period (2013) or that got delisted before the end of the study period (2022) were deselected, thus the final sample size consists of 50 manufacturing firms selected from the 6 sectors.

3.4 Sources of Data

This study employed secondary data sourced from the Nigerian Stock Exchange Fact books and related companies' annual financial reports for the periods. In this study we employed secondary data source which has been justified by recent studies of Jayeola, Agbatogun and Akinrinlola (2017). The data for the sampled manufacturing listed companies were sourced from Nigerian Exchange Group Fact Books and related companies' annual financial reports and footnotes for the periods covered in the study.

3.5 Data Analysis Technique

Data analysis involves the identification and measurement of variation in a set of variables, either among themselves or between a dependent variable and one or more independent variables (Hair Jr et al. 2014). It is important that a researcher considers the number of variables and the scale of measurement when selecting the data analysis method. A researcher must determine the research objectives, the type of data needed, the data collection method and the method of analyzing the data, and that the type of data collected determines not only whether quantitative techniques can be used but often determines the specific quantitative techniques to be used (Lancaster 2005). The levels of quantitative analysis include descriptive statistics, univariate, bivariate and multivariate analyses. However, in this study we intend to employ multivariate analysis which similar studies carried out recently by several authors have employed Shahwan and Habib 2020; Ikpesu, 2019; Jia, 2019; Vita, 2019; Umar, Faruk, Yabo and Alh 2020; Ikpesu, Vincent and Dakare 2020; Ayodeji and Okunade 2019.

3.6 Model Specification

This study specifies effective tax rate of manufacturing companies in Nigeria as a function of capital structure. To this effect, the study modifies the model of Fernández-Rodríguez and Martínez-Arias (2014) to state the econometric model of the study. Fernández-Rodríguez and Martínez-Arias (2014)'s model was stated as;

$$ETR_{it} = b_0 + b_1ETR_{it-1} + b_2SIZE_{it} + b_3LEV_{it} + b_4CAPINT_{it} + b_5 INVINT_{it} + b_6ROA_{it} + b_7YEAR + b_8INDUSTRY + v_i + e_{it}.$$

The present study modifies the above model by eliminating all non-capital structure variables and thus expresses the econometric model as:

$$CETR_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1DETA_{it} + \beta_2LTDA_{it} + \beta_3STDA_{it} + IETR_{it} + e_{it}$$

Where;

Dependent Variables

CETR = Cash Effective Tax Rate

Independent Variables

DETA	=	Leverage
LTDA	=	Long Term Debt Ratio
STDA	=	Short Term Debt Ratio

“i” for cross sections (firms in the study)

“t” for time period

e_{it} for error term

3.7 Operationalization of Variables

Table 3.2 Operationalization of Variables

Variables	Measurement	Source
Cash Effective Tax Rate	Cash effective tax in Percentage is computed as income tax paid in cash flow statement divided by profit before tax	Frank. & Goyal, (2007).
Leverage	Debt to Total Asset in percentage is computed as total liabilities divided by Total asset	Huang & Kisgen, 2013
Long Term Debt Ratio	Long Debt to Asset in percentage is computed as non-current liabilities divided by Total asset	Huang & Kisgen, 2013
Short Term Debt Ratio	Short Debt to Asset in percentage is computed as current liabilities divided by Total Asset	Custódio and Metzger (2014)

Source: Researcher’s Compilation 2025

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

The table below shows the descriptive statistics for this study.

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
ietr	468	-25.62981	224.6374	-4108.4	1179.32
deta	468	58.25846	24.71565	-17.16	224.11
ltdb	468	.1465171	.2561518	-3.37	1.04
stdb	468	.4361111	.3014289	0	3.77
cetr	468	17.9338	73.01726	-607.21	762.49

From the descriptive statistics above, it is observed that on the average income effective tax rate - 25.63 with a standard deviation of 224.64. We also find that on average leverage is 58.26 with a standard error of 24.72. Similarly, we find that on average long-term debt was 0.15 with a standard deviation from the mean as 0.26. The table also shows that on average, short-term debt was 0.44 with a standard deviation of 0.30. For the control variable, we find that on average, the cash effective tax rate was 17.93.

4.2 Correlation Analysis

Although the concepts of correlation and regression are intimately related, nevertheless they are different (Warren, 1971). Correlation may be described as the degree of association between two variables, whereas regression expresses the form of the relationship between specified values of one (the independent, exogenous, explanatory, regressor, carrier or predictor) variable and the means of all corresponding values of the second (the dependent, outcome, response variable; variable being explained) variable. In general, the study of interdependence leads to the investigation of correlations (Moore, 1980), while the study of dependence leads to the theory of regression. When the x variable is a random covariate to the y variable, that is, x and y vary together (continuous variables), we are more interested in determining the strength of the linear relationship than in prediction, and the sample correlation coefficient, r_{xy} (r), is the statistics (Aknazarova&Kafarov 1982). Generally, the literature suggests that extremely non-normal distributions can sometimes inflate Type I error rates for tests of the Pearson correlation coefficient and increasing sample size does not necessarily alleviate this problem. The power benefit of Spearman's r may be the result of rank-ordering causing outliers to contract toward the center of the distribution (Fowler, 1987; Gauthier, 2001). Upon this understanding and based on the fact that the data set followed a non-normal distribution, we employ the Spearman Rank Correlation technique to conduct the possible association between the variables of interest shown in the table below;

	ietr	deta	ltdb	stdb	cetr
ietr	1.0000 468				
deta	0.0275 468	1.0000 468			
ltdb	0.0546 468	0.4206 468	1.0000 468		
stdb	-0.0473 468	0.7080 468	-0.2260 468	1.0000 468	
cetr	-0.1942 468	-0.1724 468	-0.0941 468	-0.0484 468	1.0000 468

Table 4.2: Spearman Rank Test for Correlation

Specifically, the analysis from the spearman rank correlation showed that leverage (0.0275) and long-term debt (0.0546) are positively correlated to the dependent variable of income effective tax rate. However, it is observed that short-term debt (-0.0473) and the control variable of cash effective tax rate (-0.1942) are negatively correlated with income effective tax rate. All associations are seen to be strong hence there is room to suspect the presence of multicollinearity in the estimated model.

4.3 Regression Analysis

The study carries out Pool Least Square Regression analysis and proceed to check if the basic assumption of the pool least square regression has been violated. The results obtained from the pool least square regression is as shown in the table below;

ietr	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
deta	-11.21755	19.83512	-0.57	0.572	-50.19556	27.76046
ltdb	1079.806	1981.746	0.54	0.586	-2814.524	4974.136
stdb	1057.473	1985.702	0.53	0.595	-2844.631	4959.578
cetr	-1.518317	.1244983	-12.20	0.000	-1.762969	-1.273665
_cons	35.73086	23.3259	1.53	0.126	-10.10689	81.56861

Table 43: Pool Least Square Regression

Source: STATA'16 Output

4.4 Robust Standard Error Estimator

Ordinary Least square estimation in a linear model has been established as not robust to outliers this is because a single atypical observation can in fact cause this estimator to break down. Furthermore, the least square estimator requires a moment condition on the error distribution to be consistent. However, robust regression estimators have been introduced to overcome these problems, and they have become a standard tool in regression analysis. In this situation, normality of the error terms is in fact not needed; nor does any moment need to exist when applying robust estimators. The standard approach to statistical inference based on robust regression methods is to derive the limiting distribution of the robust estimator and to compute the standard errors of the estimated regression coefficients. The robust standard errors remain valid when the error terms are not independent and identically distributed (i.i.d) but suffer from heteroskedasticity or autocorrelation. A robust standard error consistently estimates the true standard error even in the face of non i.i.d. error terms. The most popular robust standard errors in econometrics are the White or Eicker-White standard errors (attributed to Eicker, 1967, and White, 1980), which protect against heteroskedasticity and the Newey-West standard errors (Newey and West, 1987), which are heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation consistent (HAC) estimates of the standard error. Hence, an important property of robust standard errors is that the form of the heteroskedasticity and/or autocorrelation does not need to be specified. Therefore, due to the presence of heteroscedasticity obtained from the panel least square regression estimator, the researcher proceeds to employ the Eicker-White standard errors which is relied upon for hypotheses testing. The results is presented below:

Robust regression		Number of obs	=	466
		F(4, 461)	=	27.41
		Prob > F	=	0.0000

ietr	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
deta	7.812031	2.500135	3.12	0.002	2.898957 12.72511
ltdb	-778.0156	249.7933	-3.11	0.002	-1268.89 -287.1409
stdb	-771.7413	250.2953	-3.08	0.002	-1263.603 -279.8801
cetr	-.1823011	.019326	-9.43	0.000	-.220279 -.1443232
_cons	-20.21619	2.969885	-6.81	0.000	-26.05238 -14.38

Table 4.4: Robust Pool Least Square Regression

Source: STATA'16 Output

The table above shows the result obtained from robust standard error estimator for income effective tax rate model. Specifically, the researcher provide interpretation for the robust standard error estimator as recommended by Gujarati (2004). The model's goodness of fit as captured by the Fisher statistics (27.41) and the corresponding probability value (0.00000) shows a 1% statistically significant level suggesting that the entire model is fit and can be employed for interpretation and policy recommendation.

4.5 Discussion of Findings

Tax is one of the biggest contributions to a country provided by individuals or companies as taxpayers without getting reciprocal directly; it is forcing and collecting based on law. The government uses tax to develop national structure to achieve general welfare in many sectors (Darmawan and Sukartha, 2014). The tax is also one of the biggest national income sources which comes from society. The government can develop programs which can be enjoyed by society through tax payment. According to Santoso and Ning (2013) and Nurfadilah (2016), most of the companies as taxpayers judge that tax payment is an expense, because tax source is a change from business sector or enterprise to the public sector or government which affects the obedience taxpayer to decrease.

In this study, we document a positive significant effect of leverage on effective tax rate. This implies that the ratio of equity shareholders to the total assets of the firms in our sample will increase their effective tax rate. This is in line with the studies of Kurniasih and Sari (2013). However, we negate the findings of Dharma and Ardiana (2016) Who concluded that one way to minimize tax payment is leverage because it will raise the interest costs and will reduce company profit, and the ETR will be lower. Richardson and Lanis (2007) also stated that when a company relies more on debt financing than equity to operations, a company will have a lower effective tax rate. This is because companies which have a higher debt level will pay higher tax rate. It makes the value of effective tax rate become lower.

We document significant negative effect of short-term and long-term debt on effective tax rate of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. This implies that the increase in short- and long-term debts which constitute total debt will reduce effective tax rate of the firms in our sample. Debt financing offers tax advantages for companies because interest paid on loans, in general, can be tax deductible (Koh & Lee, 2015). Therefore, the company's management will tend to use the debt at the optimal level to minimize the tax burden that must be paid. The results of the studies conducted by Salaudeen (2017), Nugraha&Meiranto (2015), Delgado et al. (2012), Noor et al. (2010), and Richardson & Lanis (2007) show that total debt has a negative influence on effective tax rate.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

The best capital structure is a tough task that management of the firm must take responsibility for. Capital structure decisions are of a high degree of importance to the organizations because they have a direct impact on firm value and stockholder's wealth. Management elected by stockholders are representatives of them in the board of directors, and they are supposed to operate in their best interests. The significance of choosing the best financing decision among the available alternatives is undeniable for the financial well-being of a firm. Capital structure decision that must be made by finance managers is one of the three financing decisions including investment, financing and dividend decisions. The optimal choice of capital structure at diverse situations among the other existing investment opportunities, which can gain the highest rate of return and the lowest cost are strongly related to firm's capability to fulfill the requests of its various stakeholders. This reality highlights the importance of capital structure decisions which are mentioned above. According to Abor and Biekpe (2005), capital structure decision is essential due to the necessity of maximizing returns to numerous organizational stakeholders and the effect of this decision on an organization's

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capability to deal with its competitors. This study examined the effect of capital structure on effective tax rate of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Results from the robust standard error estimator leads to the conclusion that leverage can increase effective tax rate while short-term and long-term debt reduces the effective tax rate of the firms under consideration.

This study recommends that governments be stricter in overseeing firm tax policies and practices by exploiting the loopholes contained in the taxation rules, one of which is by applying capital structure practices. Further studies are expected to examine other proxies such as liquidity, capital intensity, and inventory intensity to further enrich the discussion of effective tax rate. Future researchers can then add non-financial factors, such as corporate governance that can influence effective tax rate. In addition, for further studies the author suggests that the book-tax difference (BTD) be used as a proxy for effective tax.

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